

Tricresyl Phosphate Measurement Methods Used to Identify Flight Crew and Passenger Exposure

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ABBREVIATIONS

TCP

Tri-Cresyl Phosphate

ABSTRACT

Measurement TCP isomers in aircraft environments indicates jet engine oil exposure from bleed air. The neurotoxic, and other, effects associated with these agents make it imperative that exposure measurements are done accurately. Wipe samples are an indicator of the presence of, rather than exposure to, agents. Air sampling is an indicator of inhalation exposure but varies between methods. The VN air sampler was ideal to capture rare bleed air events.

Carbon monoxide, formaldehyde, and ultrafine particulates need monitoring. Axonal transport of ultrafine particles by the olfactory nerve was postulated as one possible route of exposure of the CNS to TCP.

INTRODUCTION

The measurement of Tri-Cresyl Phosphate (TCP) isomers in aircraft has been very important in identifying bleed air as a source of TCP contamination. The highly specific isomer profile of jet turbine oils provides a direct link to turbine oils as the source of this air contamination.

Since TCP isomers are known to affect the central and peripheral nervous systems, accurate measurements

need to be made in order to assess the level of exposure and the risk that is associated with that exposure. In addition to TCP exposure, a large number of additional agents, referred to as pyrolysis products, which have been identified and are also associated with bleed air events. Measuring TCP in aircraft therefore serves two major purposes, it indicates exposure to a neurotoxic agent as well as to pyrolysis products from engine oils that are generated along with TCP release during a bleed air event.^{1,2}

Typical TCP isomer patterns from jet turbine oils are shown in Figure 1. When this pattern is found in aircraft it identifies the source of TCP i.e., jet turbine oils.³

Various sampling strategies have been used to identify TCP isomers in aircraft. These include, filters from the environmental control systems within the aircraft, clothing from occupants, coalescer bags, dust samples, hair samples, sedimentation cards, surface wipe samples, and air samples. Of these, wipe samples and air samples will be further explored in this article.

Wipe samples

Surface wipe samples can be a good indicator of what has sedimented from the air onto a surface and hence what individuals breathing the air were exposed to. This means that we need to know that the surface being wiped was free of contaminants prior to flight. This is only possible with the use of sedimentation cards. Wipe samples from surfaces within the aircraft, unless shown not to be exposed to TCP prior to flight, only show potential exposure which can be over an extended period of time depending on housekeeping procedures used in the aircraft. Wipe sample procedures have been standardized, the procedure can be found in the ASTM website.

It can be observed that the surface wiped from the A380 #3 was an order of magnitude lower in contaminants than A380 #4. Having no information as to who, how well, and where, these samples were collected, no further conclusions can be drawn from these samples at this point.

Figure 1 – TCP isomer patterns from jet turbine oils

The specific ion monitoring mode (SIM) for the TCP, i.e. the 368 ion, of these two samples show some interesting results.

It can be observed from the lower trace that all the peaks from the standard are represented indicating that jet turbine oil was the source of contamination. In addition, one can see the presence of a number of additional peaks that have the same molecular weight of TCP. These additional peaks are likely the other TCP isomers that were not found in the turbine oils. If this is indeed the case the presence of these isomers might indeed be evidence of molecular rearrangement of the four original TCP isomers in turbine oil. The physical conditions at the bleed port of the engine are such, i.e. 170 psi and 350°C, that molecular rearrangement is possible. This is further substantiated by the presentation from David Johnson who describes additional conditions present in the micro-environment of the actual bearing lubricated

surface. He concluded from his research that molecular disintegration and rearrangement are likely to occur under these conditions.

Before we can come to those conclusions based on these chromatograms one needs to eliminate a couple of variables, such as the possible presence of these additional isomers in the Eastman 2197 jet turbine oil. An analysis of this oil has not been done yet in our laboratory. Another variable that needs attention is the possibility that the plastic surface, that was wiped, was a source of these additional isomers.

The 12 wipe sample analyses from 12, A380 aircraft indicate that ten were positive for TCP isomers range 3.2-41.4 nanograms per wipe, all 12 wipes samples were positive for tributylphosphate (TBP), a component of hydraulic fluid, range 5.6-108.9 ng/wipe. Seven wipes showed a “hint” of the additional isomers discussed above.

A380 #3

A380 #4

Figure 2 — Analysis of wipe samples. The results from the full scan gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GCMS) analysis of wipe samples from interior surfaces of two A380 aircraft that were given to our laboratory for analysis.

Direct air sampling

Air sampling for volatile organic compounds (VOCs) are usually done using sorbent tubes filled with a large number of different sorbents such as Tenax, Chromosorb, charcoal, etc.⁴ Non-volatile and semi-volatile compounds are usually collected on a number of substrates, such as quartz (fiberglass) filters. Recently two reports have been published that make reference to the use of sorbent tubes to measure TCP isomers

in the air of aircraft,⁵ and TNO in the Netherlands.⁶ Their descriptions of the methods used to monitor TCP in aircraft air are not specific enough to allow the reader to replicate their procedures leaving it open for speculation. In order to find out what they possibly could have measured, or not measured, we generated a TCP environment in an environmental chamber where we compared Chromosorb 106 tubes ability to capture TCP from the air along with the VN sampler, which uses 37

Figure 3 — SIM of Ion 368, of a wipe sample from an A380 aircraft. Top trace is the laboratory standard, lower trace shows the results from the wipe sample

Figure 4 — Example of a sorbent tube

Figure 5 — Environmental setup to compare TCP capturing efficiency

mm Quartz filters (Whatmann).

Typical diagram of a sorbent tube, such as used by some to measure airborne TCP is shown in Figure 4. Environmental setup to compare TCP capturing efficiency is shown in Figure 5.

It was observed that the amount of TCP trapped on the sorbent, Chromosorb 106, was only 8.1-8.3% compared to the amount that was collected under the same conditions on the Quartz filter. If all contents of the Chromosorb tubes were analyzed, i.e. sorbent and fiberglass, the sorbent tubes were only 52- 60% as efficient as the fiberglass filters. The separators in the

tubes did not contain foam as shown in Figure 4 but were fiberglass. Foam separators have been shown in the past to be contaminated with a chlorinated organophosphate called Fyrol-PCF.⁷

Filter arrangements normally include a pump attached by means of a tygon tube to a cassette filter holder which can be placed in an area to be monitored. After exposure, the technician removes the cassette filter holder from the tygon tubing and covers the in, and outlets, with small plastic plugs. As this arrangement is quite cumbersome and requires the presence of a trained technician, a self-contained sampling pump and filter assembly was therefore developed and tested for use in aircraft which can be used by anyone.⁸ This air sampler is shown in Figure 6.

This patented air sampler, often referred to as the “VN sampler” has been tested and complies with the FAA regulations for use during all phases of flight (CKC).

Reference to this sampler by De Boer *et al.* in the peer reviewed journal *Chemosphere* is incorrect as they refer to the sampler as using Chromosorb 106 sorbent tubes.⁹

The VN sampler has been, and currently is, used by pilots who have experienced an abnormal smell event within the aircraft without being able to provide objective evidence that this actually occurred during flight. Pilots travel with these samplers on a stand-by basis to be activated when they sense an abnormality in the air.

Recently two samplers were returned to our lab for analysis. These samplers came from an A380, the captain of which sensed a peculiar abnormal smell. Upon analysis we identified high levels of an abnormal agent Bis(2-ethylhexyl)adipate. A search of this agent in the literature identified it as an aircraft lubricant and a plasticizer.

The results from this observation clearly show that the often-used argument by the industry, that it is virtually impossible to obtain and capture accurate data during these highly sporadic events, is faulty. To date, with only

a small number of these samplers flying across the globe on standby, we have captured a number of smell events and identified their source. Some of these were traced to hydraulic fluid, another to disinsectants overuse, a third to TCP bleed air and the current Bis(2-ethylhexyl)adipate which has not been traced to a source as yet. In order to do this one requires the cooperation of the maintenance division of the operator of this aircraft. It can be concluded from these observations that not all air quality events in the aircraft are related to bleed air. It can also be concluded that the capture of abnormal air quality in aircraft is not difficult. The frequency of abnormal events in aircraft, based on the data from van Netten,¹⁰ ranged at that time, from 0.09 to 1.29 per 1000 flight cycles, and Shehadi 2016, from 0.21 to 0.78 per 1000 flight cycles. In order to capture a large number of events, one can provide, as an example, 200 pilots with one sampler each. Assuming that each pilot, on the average, experiences two flight cycles per day, that would amount to 400 flight cycles having been monitored. After 100 days 40,000 flight cycles are monitored. Using the lowest frequency of 0.21/1000,¹¹ this would capture 8.4 events. At the higher frequency of 0.78/1000 flight cycles this would capture 31.2 events. This would provide a rich, objective, data base to help the understanding of abnormal air events in aircraft. This data, which is currently missing, can be used to provide a realistic basis for simulation experiments.

Other agents of interest that need to be monitored are gases, specifically, carbon monoxide (CO) and formaldehyde. Of these CO is the deadliest of the two as this gas causes incapacitation without warning unlike formaldehyde which is a respiratory irritant causing flu like symptoms, sore throat and headaches. Figure 7 shows the temperature dependence of the generation of formaldehyde and carbon monoxide from various oils and fluids.

Additional areas of exposure that need to be monitored

It has been observed by Yang *et al.* that airborne TCP is associated with ultrafine particulate matter, particles <0.1 nanometers.¹² This is consistent with our observations and actual measurements in our environmental chamber,

Figure 6 — Air sampler

*Lowest temperature where the following parameters can be observed or measured
Fumes= visible fumes, CO = Carbon monoxide
HCHO = Formaldehyde.

**Engine temperatures during different phases of flight were obtained from: Boeing, July 13, 2001 in NAS, The Airliner Cabin Environment and the Health of Passengers and Crew, 2002,

Figure 7 — Heat stability of some hydraulic fluids and jet engine lubricating oils at 760 mm Hg

Figure 8 — The olfactory nerve

that airborne TCP exists as an aerosol and can be trapped on fiberglass filters. These nano particles can bypass the blood brain barrier by using axonal transport of the olfactory nerve.¹³⁻¹⁶ Axonal transport by the olfactory nerve has been used in medicine to deliver specific drugs to CNS targets.¹⁷

It is interesting to note that the olfactory nerve, Figure 8, ends in the olfactory tubercle which ends right at the region of the brain that is responsible for cognition, depression, and Parkinson's disease like syndromes, i.e. symptoms that have been reported by numerous pilots after exposure to alleged bleed air events.¹⁸⁻²⁰

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